

Role of Parental Influence on Bullying Tendencies among High School Students

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Abstract: The study was designed to investigate which domain of parental influence best predicts bullying tendencies among high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT). Using an adapted standardized questionnaire, the researcher surveyed 266 students randomly selected using the random sampling technique. The data collected were analyzed using the mean, Pearson's r , and multiple regression. The finding of the investigation reveals that the level of parental influence is high, and the level of bullying tendencies is very low. Furthermore, when analyzed as to the relationship that exists between the two variables, the result shows that in some collective capacities, parental influence is significantly correlated, specifically the parental expectation. Alternatively, when regressed, the individual domain of parental influence that posted significantly predicts bullying tendencies is parental expectation. The finding suggests that parental influence correlates with the risk of committing bullying behavior acts.

Keywords: Parental influence, bullying tendencies, Correlation, Regression, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Rationale

In every social aspect of human interaction, behavioral aggression and violence have been observed not only in the Philippines but also around the world. Noticeably, one of these behavioral aggressions and violence problems is the school bullying phenomenon (Ang, Chong, Cheong, Lee, Tang, & Liew, 2018; Sargin, 2017). According to the survey published by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (Program for International Student Assessment [PISA], 2018), the Philippines was among the participating countries that reported the most cases of bullying globally. Statistically, 6 of 10 high school students have been reported as being bullied. Thus, these current issues are alarming how primordial it is to study since school bullying can lead to distress, worries, and troubles for both bully and victims and the parents, teachers, and school environment as well (Sargin, 2017). When not adequately addressed, the bullied individual might drop out of school and risk committing criminal behavior.

Correspondingly, the victims will experience trauma, withdrawal, loneliness, fear, avoidance of school, depression, and risk of suicide ideation and attempt (Craven, 2014). Therefore, with this worrying effect of bullying, prevention programs are seriously important. Indeed, identifying tendencies is one of the essential interventions to prevent bullying in the classroom or in schools (Sargin, 2017). Several studies have unequivocally established factors that influence bullying tendencies or bullying behavior. One of these well-known factors is parental influence. Several authors have stated that when a parent treats their children in a domineering manner, using excessive punishments, imposing many prohibitions, and enforcing strict rules, their children are more likely to exhibit unfriendly, hostile, aggressive, and bullying behaviors. As a result, they develop a rebellious and non-compliant personality and engage in bullying acts (Ajani & Dosunmu, 2018; Chiarlitti & Kolen, 2017; Sargin, 2017). These concur with the propositions of numerous experts (Tajuddin, Utami, & Arafat, 2017; Efobi & Nwokolo, 2014; Shetgiri, Lin, Avila, & Flores, 2012; Schmuck, 2011; Knous-Westfall, Ehrensaft, MacDonell, & Cohen, 2012) who confirmed the significant relationship between parental influence and the tendency to bullying behavior as well as its impact. They have claimed that the lack of good parenting practices, lack of parental communication, support, pressure, and discipline significantly lead to children's risk of committing bullying behavior or doing bullying deeds. Likewise, this confirms Swearer and Hymel's (2015) findings that when a child is abused, exposed to intimate partner violence, poor parental supervision, lack of parental communication, lack of parental emotional support, negative family environment, parental conflict, and domestic violence, parental abuse, authoritarian parenting, and inappropriate discipline contribute to bullying perpetration.

The problem of bullying behavior is currently visible among the high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology. This valid observation sparked a growing interest for the researchers to engage in this study urgently since several cases and bullying have already been reported at the school's guidance office. These bullying acts include fighting in the classroom, provocation, threatening aggressive behavior, verbal abuse, and cyber bullying.

While there were several studies related to parental influence and bullying tendencies, however, no studies had been conducted as of yet that parental influence incorporating parental expectation, parental discipline, and parental communication that correlates with bullying tendencies integrating physical, verbal, psychological, social, and cyber bullying tendencies, especially in the context of a Catholic school in Valencia City, Bukidnon.

1.2 Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine which domain of parental influence best influences the bullying tendencies among high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology. Specifically, it intends to achieve the following objectives:

- ✓ To describe the level of parental influence in terms of expectation, discipline, and communication.
- ✓ To determine the level of bullying tendencies in terms of physical bullying, verbal bullying, psychological bullying, social bullying, and cyberbullying.
- ✓ To establish the significance of the relationship between parental influence and bullying tendencies among high school students;
- ✓ To identify which domain of parental influence best predicts bullying tendencies of high school students.

1.3 Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1 There is no significant relationship between parental influence and bullying tendencies.

Ho2 There is no domain in parental influence best predicts bullying tendencies.

1.4 Significance of the Study

Generally, this study is significant to its beneficiaries since it would provide valuable information on the relationship between the study's independent and dependent variables. Moreover, it would inform the readers of this study on whether the parental influence is a significant predictor of bullying tendencies. Specifically, this study is beneficial for the following:

Students. This study will be beneficial to the students to let them know their behavior in relation to bullying possibilities and reinforce their awareness of the risk of committing bullying behavior towards their classmates or schoolmates. It might be used as an eye-opener to know their parent's level of expectation, discipline, and communication. Lastly, it will be a great realization for them that their parents could influence their tendency to engage in bullying behavior.

Parents. The result of this study will be beneficial to the parents to help them know their children's level of bullying tendency. It will also serve as a hint for them on how their children perceive their parental expectations, discipline, and

communication. Likewise, it will serve as information to improve their guidance, supervision, and discipline, especially when their children have high possibilities of bullying behavior.

School. This study will be beneficial to the school personnel, especially the teacher and guidance counselor, to create intervention plans, give support, and educate their students on the effect and consequences of bullying behavior. The study's findings will open an opportunity for the educators to work with their students to build character or have a positive connection with each other as an intervention to convert their misbehavior and thus become well-mannered.

Future Researcher. This study is significant as an addition to the body of knowledge for future researchers about parental influence and bullying tendencies.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section presents the review of related literature, which has a significant bearing on the conduct of the present study. The discussion in this section is organized according to the variables of the study, which include: parental influence on specific domains, parental expectation, parental discipline, parental communication, and bullying tendencies in terms of physical, verbal, psychological, social, and cyberbullying tendencies. This is immediately followed by the correlation between measures.

2.1 Parental Influence

Parental influence is defined as a parent's acquired behavior and attitudes influencing or molding children's behavior, attitudes, and characteristics based on their parenting style, involvement, care, communication, discipline, expectation or pressure, motivation/encouragement, and support, which can affect them negatively or positively. Optimistically, this can be a source of inspiration, encouragement, and stimulus for students to do well in school and behave properly. In contrast, if it is not well managed, their children become unfriendly, hostile, aggressive, and tend to have bullying behaviors (Ajani & Dosunmu, 2018; Chiarlitti & Kolen, 2017; Schmuck, 2011). In this current study, parental influence encompasses or is integrated with *parental expectations, parental discipline, and parental communication* (Black, 2014).

2.1.1 Parental Expectation

Various authors defined parental expectation as a realistic belief or judgment that parents have about their children's future achievement as reflected in course grades, the highest level of schooling attained, or college attendance (Yamamoto & Holloway, 2010; Ma, Siu, and Tse, 2018). Parenting expectation can be contrasted with parental aspiration, which typically refers to desires, wishes, or goals that parents have formed regarding their children's future attainment rather than what they expect their children to achieve. A previous study of well-known authors (Yamamoto et al., 2010; Loughlin-Presnal and Bierman, 2017) discovered the effect of parental expectation on their children's academic achievement. They stipulated that parents' expectations of cultivating a child's early learning behavior by encouraging, persevering, and praising their efforts to develop new skills. As a result, parents' expectations increased their children's behavioral engagement, challenged them to complete their tasks, and fostered accelerated growth in their academic performance through effort or determination. However, parental expectations have had a significant influence on adolescents' depression. The occurrence happens because some parents put too much pressure on their children which can lead to stress and depression (Yamamoto et al., 2010; Ma, Sui & Tse, 2018; Loughlin-Presnal et al., 2018).

2.1.2 Parental Discipline

Parental discipline is defined as a method or technique used by parents to control and prevent their children's misbehavior, guide and teach them, and make them behave through positive approaches. However, this discipline includes psychological or emotional harm or threats to their children because sometimes parents incorporate discipline with excessive punishment or become abusive in their punishment (Zolotor, Theodore, Runyan, Chang & Laskey, 2011). Some statistical findings showed that maternal and paternal disciplinary practices correlated with childbirth order, child emotionality, attention span, persistence, perceived social support and quality of life, and retrospective punitive parenting (Moon, Kim, Seay, Small & Kim, 2016). Moreover, some experts exposed dysfunctional levels of disciplinary (harsh or lax parenting discipline style) use that were associated with children who displayed more behavior problems. Dysfunctional parenting practices, if not improved, could exacerbate problematic child behavior following acquired brain injury (ABI) that may cause the parent and family difficulties. Some authors suggested that parental assessment may be useful as a method of screening for parental factors that put children at risk for ongoing behavior problems and families for ongoing stress (Woods, Catroppa, & Anderson, 2011).

2.1.3 Parental Communication

Communication is part of our being. Communication is sending information from one person to another, which can be verbal or non-verbal, positive or negative, or effective or ineffective. Communication is the engine of social relationships, and it depends on the quality of the relationship. Communication involves listening, availability, understanding, mutual respect, and emotion (Zolten & Pillay, 2006). This communication is vital in the parent-child relationship since many authors asserted that the quality of communication among family members contributes to the quality of the parent-child relationship, which predicts children's well-being. Therefore, *Parental communication* refers to the ability of family members to exchange their needs, feelings, and desires with one another and attend to the changing needs of family members positively. Open parent-child communication is one aspect of a good parent-child relationship that plays a critical role in maintaining the healthy function of the family system and children's development. Moreover, communication is fundamental for maintaining and supporting close family relationships, and it contributes effective qualities to the parent-child relationship (Runcan, Constantineanu, Ielics, & Popa, 2012). Through communication, parents can identify, know and then satisfy the real needs of their children. Communication between parents and children contributes significantly to creating fair and effective relationships, understanding, and mutual acceptance between parents and children. Therefore, it is significant for parents to know how to communicate with their children effectively and openly.

2.2 Bullying Tendencies

Bullying was widely studied across different countries. In general, bullying can be found in different settings or situations. It can be seen in the workplace, community, home, and, most commonly, in classrooms or schools (Craven, 2014; Antiri, 2014). By definition, bullying is an intentional and repetitive occurrence of intimidation and uses unbalanced force on someone that requires tendency (Sargin, 2017). Henceforth, the present study focus on bullying in the classroom or in schools. Through identifying the tendency of bullying in school is an important prevention strategy. Accordingly, it will help schools discover students' chances of engaging in bullying behavior (Antiri, 2016). The tendency by its nature and definition;

"It is a natural inclination, bent, or predisposition to like, want or do something; an attitude determined by the feelings felt for an object or entity; a desire to achieve a certain goal due to the effect of emotions" (Sargin, 2017).

The definition proposed that tendencies are amongst the sources, roots, or causes that an individual becomes or moves, proceeds, or acts towards something in certain ways. In other words, bullying tendencies may be considered the bridge to detecting, identifying, or ascertaining the student's bullying behavior. Bullying tendencies could refer to inclination, possibility, or risk of committing aggressive bullying behavior. Thus, this present exploration was consequently aimed at shaping the tendencies toward bullying among high school students, where bullying is most common at that age. The research has important implications since it will reveal the threat circumstances by identifying tendencies of bullying, particularly in high school students. As soon as identified, there is a high probability of determining the bullying tendency that believed this bullying cases in schools could be minimized by means of preventive actions or programs to be developed against bullying (Sargin, 2017). Lastly, in this study, the bullying tendencies are measured by the following domains; *physical bullying tendency, psychological bullying tendency, verbal bullying tendency, social bullying tendency, and cyberbullying tendency.*

2.2.1 Physical Bullying Tendency

Physical bullying is considered the most visible and readily identifiable form of bullying. It is either in a direct or indirect form. The direct form of physical bullying relates to punching, kicking, or any physical harm to the human body. Moreover, the indirect form of physical bullying is when a bully takes one's possession or own property by intentionally damaging it (Antiri, 2014). According to several experts (Dogruer, 2015; Dorio, Clark, Demaray & Doll, 2015), physical bullying can be seen through specific examples of this type of aggression such as hitting, elbowing, scratching, restraining, choking, poking, twisting limbs into painful positions, hair pulling, bra-snapping, shoving/cramming into a locker, stabbing, beating up, throwing an object, taking lunch or lunch money, giving a black eye, swirly, Indian rubs, noogies, nipple twisting, jabbing, and imitating wrestling holds. Hence, *physical bullying tendency is a type of bullying tendency that refers to the inclination and possibility of committing bullying aggressive behavior that physically harms or threatens their victims.*

2.2.2 Verbal Bullying Tendency

Words from the mouth can be a powerful tool that could break an individual's spirit, especially when the speaker speaks a hurting message towards the receiver. As mentioned by several experts, when a person uses verbal language to mock, insult and embarrass the person, it is called verbal bullying. Verbal bullying incidence was more on verbal threatening, harassing, and using verbal abuse by making fun of love once and the name of the victims (Arifuddin, Suriah, Syafar, Saleh, & Jafar, 2021). Moreover, verbal bullying refers to repeated teasing, name-calling, cruel criticism, cursing, yelling, being sarcastic, insulting remarks, and verbal threats toward others (Craven, 2014; Dogruer, 2015). Verbal bullying is considered an insidious act that can destroy individual self-confidence and self-image both emotionally and psychologically and lead to anxiety and depression. To some extent, or in extreme cases, it will lead to the suicide of the victims (Antiri, 2014). Hence, *verbal bullying tendency is a type of bullying tendency that refers to an inclination or possibility of gripping verbal aggression bullying behavior towards its victims.*

2.2.3 Psychological Bullying Tendency

Psychological bullying consists of either verbal or physically aggressive behaviors that can psychologically harm the victims. The psychological bully is bending to beat a person up emotionally to make them uncomfortable, disturbed, and destabilized in mind. Intimidating someone, manipulating people, and stalking a person are all examples of psychological bullying. People in popular groups or cliques often bully people they categorize as different by excluding them or gossiping about them (Craven, 2014; Antiri, 2014; Dogruer, 2015). Consequently, students who tend to bully others at school could be the prediction to significantly subsequent antisocial and violent behavior. Several authors have reported that the reasons for bullying are that the bully is pretending to be strong, having this low psychological well-being, poor social adjustment, and psychological distress. *Psychological bullying tendency is a type of bullying tendency that refers to the inclination or possibility of committing bullying or behavioral aggression that harms or threatens the victims psychologically.*

2.2.4 Social Bullying Tendency

Social bullying, which is also known as relational bullying, incorporates repetitive psychological harm and manipulation of the social system. The author added that social bullying involves situations where the bullies might spread rumors, backbite and exclude the victim from the peer group (Antiri 2014). Social bullying is a form of emotionally aggressive behavior that occurs within the context of large groups and within small social networks, close friendships, or romantic relationships. Social bullying involves hurting someone's reputation or relationship. Social bullying can be proactive or used to achieve or maintain social position, gain attention, or alleviate boredom, or it can be reactive or retaliatory, in response to a perceived threat or a feeling of anger, jealousy, or betrayal (Stuart-Cassel, Terzian & Brandshaw, 2013). This coincided with Dogruer's (2015) that relational bullying can be related to insidious acts such as using negative body language or facial expression, gossiping, starting/spreading rumors, arranging public humiliation, playing mean tricks, insulting publicly, ruining a reputation, ignoring someone in punish or coerce exclusion, threatening to end a relationship undermining other relationships, passively not including in group ostracizing/total group rejection. The author also argued that relational bullying could be interchangeably referred to the emotional bullying. *Social bullying tendency refers to the inclination or possibilities of individuals engaging or committing aggressive bullying behavior that threatens the social or relational aspect of victims and harms them emotionally.*

2.2.5 Cyberbullying Tendency

The last measure of bullying tendency is cyberbullying tendency. Through the rise of technological advancement, cyberbullying is being separately specified as another type of bullying (Dogruer, 2015). Cyberbullying can be viewed as repetitive when a message, photograph, or video clip is taken once and sent to more than one individual who, in turn, forwards this to other people or alternatively upload the material onto a website. Every time someone accesses this site or material, it can be viewed as repetition. Cyberbullying means that a child or teen is subjected to text messages, e-mails-mails, or online posts, such as Facebook, Twitter, blogs, or other websites. These messages are sometimes cruel in nature, threatening, defamatory (saying things that are not true) and deliberately misleading (for example, claiming to be from someone other than the actual sender) (Antiri, 2014).

Likewise, it is accepted as the latest and the most dangerous subcategory of bullying, and it "is willful and repeated harm inflicted through the use of computers, cell phones, and other electronic devices." They have carefully chosen the words in the definition of cyberbullying, and this can be understood from their further explanation of the word choices afterward. Sending negative text messages on mobile phones, harassing emails-mails or instant messages, posting rude, insulting, and malicious statements to online bulletin boards or social academically networking sites and voice-mails, developing web pages with offensive content, posting on the website lies, attacks,

photos and gossip about their victims, sending ugly or threatening e-mails to drive up a victim's cell phone bill are an example of cyberbullying (Dogruer, 2015). *Likely, cyberbullying tendency is a bullying tendency that refers to the inclination or possibility of committing aggressive bullying behavior relating to threatening text messages, e-mail, or online posts, such as Facebook, Twitter, blogs, or other websites, towards its victims.*

2.3 Correlation between Measures

This section presents several studies focused on the same variables as the present study. Some of these studies revealed that these variables are associated, and some found no significant relationship existing between these variables.

The study conducted by Swearer and Hymel (2015) mentioned that aggressive modeling and poor parental supervision and support lead to bullying behavior in their children. This was supported by the study of Shetgiri, Avila, and Flores (2012), which aimed to explore the association between child, parental characteristics, and community associated with bullying. The study revealed that there is a correlation between parental mental health and parental perception of children at risk for committing bullying. They implied that parent-child communication, meeting children's friends, and academic encouragement can lower bullying tendencies or odds. They added that children who always or usually completed homework and had parents who talked with them and met all or most of their friends had lower bullying probabilities.

Another study conducted by Papanikolaou, Chatzikosma, and Kleio (2011) on these variables revealed the same result. This time, it aims to investigate whether family and the way that children are raised constitute an influencing factor in the demonstration of intimidating behaviors among children in the school environment. The outcome of this work has discovered that there is a significant association between parenting behavior which includes the discipline and upbringing approaches. This suggests that students' involvement in bullying incidents increases when there is no punishment, despite the child's misbehavior or when parents enforce the discipline methods without justification. Moreover, bullying is correlated with parents' reluctance to provide assistance on issues towards school.

The study of Zych, Baldry and Farrington (2017) also publicized that parental style was more related to the bully/victims. This emphasizes that children who were both bullies and victims tended to have authoritarian parents.

Furthermore, the proposition of Jeynes (2008) also contributed to the fact that there is an association between variables of this present study. The study was trying to investigate the correlation between parental involvement and their children's bullying behavior. The result revealed that parental involvement is related to the children's experiences of either being bullied or being discriminated against in their personal characteristics.

Likewise, this was supported by the study of Maralani, Mirnasab, and Hashemi (2019). The study aimed to examine the role of parenting styles and maternal stress in pupils' bullying and victimization. A total of 300 primary school pupils enrolled in the fourth and fifth grades participated in the study. The results showed that the parents of bullies and victims were predicted to have higher maternal stress than noninvolved pupils.

Similarly, the finding of the study also corroborated with the study of Biswas, Scott, Munir, Thomas, Huda, Hasan, and Mamun (2020), which aimed to estimate the population's level of prevalence of bullying victimization and its association with peer and parental supports among adolescents across low and middle income to high-income countries. The findings revealed that having higher levels of peer support and higher levels of parental support (e.g., understanding children's problems and knowing the importance of free time spent with children) were significantly associated with a reduced risk of bullying in both bullies and victims.

However, the study of Broll and Reynolds (2021) revealed the other way around that parental style was not necessarily associated with traditional bullying offending or victimization. Thus, this suggested that parental style is not the only factor affecting individuals' engagement in bullying. Personality traits and outside home environment also contribute risk of committing bullying behavior.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical bases of this research were lifted from diverse literature, studies, and even models that establish the relationship between parental influence and bullying tendency. The theoretical backbones of this study are the following: social learning theory, attachment theory, and social control theory.

2.4.1 Social Learning Theory

The first theory on which this study is anchored is the social learning theory of Bandura (1977), as cited by Chen, Wang, and Hung (2015). The theory suggests that people can learn new behaviors by observing others. This theory is based on the idea that we learn from our interactions with others in a social context. It considers that people learn from one another, including such concepts as observational learning, imitation, and modeling.

Unconnectedly, by observing the behaviors of others, people develop similar behaviors. After observing the behavior of others, people assimilate and imitate that behavior, especially if their observational experiences are positive ones or include rewards related to the observed behavior. Deming and Johnson (2019), Nabavi (2012), and Ormrod (1999) posited that observational learning can have a powerful effect and that the effect is enhanced when the observers believe that the person demonstrating the behavior is similar to themselves; a "similar other."

Using this theory, the learning from the interaction in a social context (observational learning) can be related to parental influence. Students affect their behaviors by observing and experiencing their parent's behaviors. The outcomes such as students' belief that exhibiting this behavior similar to their parents relate to bullying tendency. This was validated by known experts (Knous-Westfall et al., 2012) that when a child experiences parental abuse, parental intimate partner violence, and a lack of good parenting practices, the child tends to engage in bullying and behavioral aggression. Also, this theory was confirmed by the study of Swearer and Hymel (2015). They argued that the characteristics of the family such as poor parental supervision, lack of parental communication, lack of parental emotional support, negative family environment, parental conflict and domestic violence, parental abuse, authoritarian parenting, and inappropriate discipline contributed or were associated with bullying perpetration.

2.4.2 Attachment Theory

The second theoretical backbone of this study is the attachment theory of Bowlby (1907-1990), as cited by Bretherton (1985). This theory discussed the parent-child relationships. It is a psychological, evolutionary, and ethological theory concerning relationships between humans. The most significant principle in this theory is that young children need to bond with at least one primary caregiver for normal social and emotional development. Attachment theories addressed the establishment, maintenance, and consequences of the affectionate relationship of a child towards his parents. In the context of this study, this affectionate relationship of the parents towards their children could be related to parental influence, specifically in the ways how parents discipline, communicate, support, and care for their children in addressing behavioral, psychological, and emotional development.

2.4.3 Social Control Theory

The third theory on which this study is anchored in the social control theory. Social control theory was developed by Hirschi (1969) as cited by Houser (2021). It is also known as the social bond theory. Under the social control theory, individuals break the law due to a breakdown of their societal bond. It refers to four elements that constitute the societal bond such as *attachment* to those both within and outside of the family, including friends, teachers, and co-workers; *commitment* to activities in which an individual has invested time and energy, such as educational or career goals; *involvement* in activities that serve to both further bonds an individual to others and leave limited time to become involved in deviant activities; and finally, *belief* in wider social values. The theory assumed that crime or lawbreaking behavior occurred as a result of weak social bonds. Simply put, the stronger one's social bonds to the conventional society, the lesser likelihood that he/she will engage in activities that are against societal norms.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of this study. This study involves two variables, of which one is independent and the other is dependent. Parental influence, the independent variable of the study, comprises the following domains; *parental expectation, parental discipline, and parental communication*. The dependent variable is bullying tendency measured by the following domains; *physical bullying tendency, psychological bullying tendency, verbal bullying tendency, social bullying tendency, and cyberbullying tendency*.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing the relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

III. METHODS

This chapter presents the methodological approaches and activities undertaken by the researchers to ensure the rigor and achievement of the study objectives. The presentation covers the research design, research locale, population and sample, research instrument, scoring procedure, data collection, statistical treatment, and ethical consideration.

3.1 Research Design

This research used a quantitative, non-experimental research design utilizing the descriptive-correlational technique. This approach highlights target estimations and statistical, mathematical, or numerical investigation through a survey. It assesses a phenomenon through statistical analysis (Creswell, 2014). Thus, using descriptive-correlational methods establishes the association between two variables, in this case, parental influence and bullying tendencies.

A non-experimental research design is a way that does not rely on manipulating independent variables. In this method, the respondents were not randomly assigned to conditions or orders of conditions. The purpose of non-experimental methods is to investigate and explain real-life experiences and current phenomena. Commonly, non-experimental studies are observational, and the results are intended to describe using a survey questionnaire. In this study, the observations were made to establish how parental influence and bullying tendencies are related and affect one another (Creswell, 2014).

This study also utilized the descriptive-correlational research method. The approach is concerned with describing the nature, trends, frequencies, characteristics, and categories of a phenomenon. Descriptive research involves gathering data that describe events and then organizing, tabulating, depicting, and analyzing the data collected without any manipulation of variables and/or aimed at discovering inference or causal relationship between two variables. Further, the correlational research method was used to measure and evaluate the positive and negative relationship between variables (Creswell, 2014).

Overall, the study applied a quantitative, non-experimental, using the correlational technique because the researchers are looking for students' perception of how well they perceive parental influence and whether or not it has any impact on bullying tendencies. The goal of utilizing a quantitative study is to determine whether the domains under parental influence are significantly correlated and could influence bullying tendencies in the context of San Agustin Institute of Technology.

3.2 Research Locale

This study was conducted at San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT), Fr. Manlio Caroselli S.J. Street, Poblacion, Valencia City, Bukidnon. This school is a private Catholic institution founded by an Italian missionary priest, Fr. Manlio Caroselli S.J., in 1960. The school offers complete educational services; preschool, grade school, Junior and Senior High school, and college.

3.3 Population and Sample

The respondents of the study were high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology. The researchers chose them as the respondents of the study since the focus of the present study is on the risk of committing bullying. Probability sampling was employed to determine the sample of the study. Probability sampling is also known as "random sampling." This sampling technique permits every single item from the universe to have an equal chance of presence in the sample (Etikan & Bala, 2017). Using Raosoft – an online sample size calculator, the researchers randomly selected 289 but only reached 266 respondents out of 1,156 total populations.

3.4 Statistical Treatment

These are the following statistical tools used to analyze and treat data collected. *Mean, Pearson r moment correlation, and Multiple Regression Analysis.*

3.5 Ethical Consideration

The researchers made sure that ethical protocols in the conduct of the research were observed. Permission from the school principal and classroom advisers and consent from the respondents were sought first before the conduct of the study. Respondents were fully informed of the study's objectives and the possible risks entailed in the conduct of the study. Respondents were encouraged to participate in the study but were never coerced to do so if they refused to. In other words, the researchers ensured that all respondents who answered the questionnaires participated in the study voluntarily. The researchers ensured that the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents' personal information were properly observed. No personal information from the respondents was divulged, no data in the study was falsified and fabricated, and any form of deceit was avoided. Also, to ensure the originality of this study, the researchers had their manuscript examined with plagiarism software. All these ethical issues were avoided, and the researchers observed all these ethical protocols to develop a quality and ethically-bound study.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the result of the analysis made on the data collected. The presentation order is as follows: level of parental influence; level of bullying tendencies; the correlation between parental influence and bullying tendencies; regression analysis between parental influence and bullying tendencies; and the conclusion and recommendation.

4.1 Level of Parental Influence

Established in Table 1 is the summary of the level of parental influence among high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT). The overall mean for parental influence is 3.75, described as "agree" with a standard deviation of 0.72. The result suggests that the students have manifested the items on parental influence as frequently observed.

Table 1: Level of Parental Influence

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Parental Expectation	3.97	0.67	Frequently Observed
Parental Communication	3.84	0.72	Frequently Observed
Parental Discipline	3.45	0.78	Frequently Observed
Category Mean	3.75	0.72	Frequently Observed

Legend:

Scale	Limits	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Always observed
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	Frequently observed
3	2.61-3.40	Agree nor Disagree	Sometimes observed
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Seldom observe
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Never observed at all

4.2 Level of Bullying Tendencies

Displayed in Table 2 is the summary of the level of bullying tendencies among high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT). The overall mean for bullying tendencies is 1.44, described as "never," with a standard deviation of 0.64. The result suggests that the students have manifested the items on bullying tendencies as extremely low.

Table 2: Level of Bullying Tendencies

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Verbal Bullying Tendency	1.56	0.68	Extremely Low
Social Bullying Tendency	1.48	0.72	Extremely Low
Physical Bullying Tendency	1.47	0.66	Extremely Low
Psychological Bullying Tendency	1.44	0.65	Extremely Low
Cyber Bullying Tendency	1.27	0.65	Extremely Low
Category Mean	1.44	0.64	Extremely Low

Legend:

Scale	Limits	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Always	Extremely high
4	3.41-4.20	Frequently	High
3	2.61-3.40	Sometimes	Not high nor low
2	1.81-2.60	Seldom	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Never	Extremely low

4.3 Correlation Analysis between Parental Influence and Bullying Tendencies

Displayed in Table 3 is the test of correlation to determine the significant relationship between parental influence and bullying tendencies in the context of high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT). Results revealed that out of the three domains of parental influence, the parental expectation was negatively correlated with all the indicators of bullying tendencies with the r-value of -0.166 and p-value of 0.011 on *physical bullying tendency*; r-value of -0.233 and p-value of 0.000 on *verbal bullying tendency*; r-value of -0.165 and p-value of 0.012 on *psychological bullying tendency*; r-value of -0.159 and p-value of 0.015 for *social bullying tendency*; and an r-value of -0.140 and a p-value of 0.034 on *cyber bullying tendency* which is lesser than the 0.05 level (2-tailed) level of significance. This denotes that upon the aggregate and individual capacity, parental influence has a significant negative correlation towards bullying tendencies. Hence, the first null hypothesis stated, "There is no significant relationship between parental influence and bullying tendencies among the high school students," is rejected.

Table 3: Correlation between Parental Influence and Bullying Tendencies

Parental influence	Bullying Tendencies					Interpretation
	Physical Bullying Tendency	Verbal Bullying Tendency	Psychological Bullying Tendency	Social Bullying Tendency	Cyber Bullying Tendency	
<i>Parental Expectation</i>	<i>-.166*</i> <i>(.011)</i>	<i>-.233**</i> <i>(.000)</i>	<i>-.165*</i> <i>(.012)</i>	<i>-.159*</i> <i>(.015)</i>	<i>-.140*</i> <i>(.034)</i>	<i>Significant</i>
Parental Discipline	-.022 (.739)	-.095 (.149)	-.035 (.596)	-.067 (.310)	-.034 (.611)	Not Significant
Parental Communication	-.026 (.699)	-.128 (.051)	-.088 (.183)	-.086 (.191)	-.010 (.833)	Not Significant

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

4.4 Regression Analysis on the Impact of Parental Influence on Bullying Tendencies

Established in Table 4 is the result of the test of influence conducted between parental influence and bullying tendencies using multi-regression analysis. When the test was done, the result confirmed which domain of parental influence significantly predicted the bullying tendencies among high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT). Hence, the result revealed that the F-value is 3.154 and the p-value is 0.026, which is lesser than the

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0.05 level of significance. This suggests that parental influence significantly predicts bullying tendencies in both comprehensive and individual measurements. Therefore, the null hypothesis, "There is no domain of parental influence that best predicts the bullying tendencies among the high school students," is rejected.

Moreover, the R-square value of 0.40 implies that 40% of the variance of high school students' bullying tendencies is attributed to and can be explained by parental expectation. This likewise denotes that 60% of the variance can be attributed to factors not covered in this study. Thus, the computed S-value of 0.626 is the measure of the accuracy of the prediction. The smaller its value, the better.

When examined independently, only parental expectations showed a significant negative influence on bullying tendencies. This means that the higher the level of parental influence in terms of parental expectation, the lower the bullying tendencies. Therefore, the domain of parental influence that best predicts bullying tendencies is *parental expectation*.

Table 4: Regression Analysis on the Influence of Parental Influence and Bullying Tendencies

Parental Influence (Indicators)	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value	Interpretation
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta			
	(Constant)	2.042	0.259			
Parental Expectation	-0.232	0.083	-0.246	-2.803	0.005	Significant
Parental Discipline	0.053	0.084	0.065	0.634	0.527	Not Significant
Parental Communication	0.037	0.103	0.042	0.356	0.722	Not Significant
	R		.200 ^a			
	R ²		.400			
	F		3.154			
	p		0.026 ^b			
	S		0.626			

*p<.05

V. DISCUSSION AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATION

This chapter presents the discussion of the results of the study with supporting literature for substantiation. The order of discussion is as follows: parental influence; bullying tendencies; the significant relationship between parental influence and bullying tendencies; and the significant impact of parental influence on bullying tendencies.

5.1 Parental Influence

The high level of parental influence among the high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT) is perceived due to the high rating given by the respondents on *parental expectation*, *parental discipline*, and *parental communication*. This suggests that the students often perceived their parents as proud, appreciative, not strict, and never pressured or expected too much in their academic performance and grades. They also perceived that their parents discipline them in a good way, support and track them, especially on the academic requirements and activities, talk to them often about their school experience and plan, and motivate or encourage them to become successful. These parents' behavior and attitudes are expected to increase the level of positive parental influence, which is parallel with the result of the proposition of several experts (Ajani & Dosunmu, 2018; Chiarlitti & Kolen, 2017) who highlighted that a high level of positive parental influence is associated with good parenting style, active involvement, and communication with their children, caring, upright disciplining methods, lowering expectations or pressure, motivating, as well as encourage, and support their children at all times. This further indicates that when a parent possesses a positive level of parental influence, it affects the children's behavior, attitudes, and characteristics in a positive manner.

5.2 Bullying Tendencies

The very low level of bullying tendencies among high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT) is due to the rating provided by the students regarding their perceptions of *physical bullying tendency, verbal bullying tendency, psychological bullying tendency, social bullying tendency, and cyberbullying tendency*. The result suggests that the students never intimidated, showed aggressive behavior, humiliated, insulted, frightened, and threatened their classmates or someone physically, verbally, socially, psychologically, and on social media, especially those they do not like. These students' behavior and attitudes are expected to reduce the level of bullying tendencies. Thus, the findings are congruent with the propositions of several experts (Sargin, 2017; Yuksel-Sahin, 2015), which emphasize that when students or children have a low bullying tendency, it means that they have low aggressive behavior. They likewise emphasized that the majority of students do not have serious behavioral problems or have any negative behavior. This could indicate that the majority of the students are fully aware of the effect of doing bullying acts and the punishments that shall be imposed. Likewise, this is also an indication that the school promotes a good social relationship environment for its students.

5.3 Significant Relationship between Parental Influence and Bullying Tendencies

In an aggregate and individual capacity, the test of relationship revealed that parental influence has a significant negative relationship with bullying tendencies. This means that there is an inverse association between parental influence and bullying tendencies; thus, the increased level of parental influence constitutes lower bullying tendencies. This further denotes that when the parents show good communication, positive discipline, and most importantly, having a positive expectations is linked to lower bullying tendencies. This result is supported by the works of several researchers (Ajani & Dosunmu, 2018; Chiarlitti & Kolen, 2017; Yuksel-Sahina, 2014; Papanikolaou, Chatzikosma, & Kleio, 2011) who claim that when a parent treats their children in a domineering manner, excessive punishments, impose many prohibitions and too strict rules are likely to lead their children to exhibit unfriendly, hostile, aggressive and bullying behaviors. They develop a rebellious and non-compliant kind of personality and engage in bullying acts.

Additionally, the findings of this study coincide with the ideas of some experts (Tajuddin, Utami, & Arafat, 2017; Efobi & Nwokolo, 2014; Shetgiri, Lin, Avila, & Flores, 2012; Knous-Westfall, Ehrensaft, MacDonell, & Cohen, 2012; Baldry, Farrington, & Sorrentino 2017) that lack of good parenting practices, lack of parental communication, supports, pressure and disciplines significantly underwrite child's risk of committing bullying behavior or doing bullying deeds.

In the same way, the result is aligned with the proposition of Swearer and Hymel (2015) that when a child experiences abuse, exposed to intimate partner violence, poor parental supervision, lack of parental communication, lack of parental emotional support, negative family environment, parental conflict and domestic violence, parental abuse, authoritarian parenting, and inappropriate discipline, it contributed or is associated with bullying perpetration.

Further, this was also supported by the study by Shetgiri, Avila, and Flores (2012), which found that parental characteristics, including parental health, perception, and communication, correlate to the risk of committing bullying. They added that parent-child communication, meeting children's friends, and encouraging children in their academic endeavors can lower bullying tendencies or odds. And they said that children who always or usually completed homework and had parents who talked with them and met all or most of their friends had lower bullying probabilities.

When assessed independently, only the parental expectation shows significant association with all domains of bullying tendencies. This means that in this context of the study, parental expectation is the most important indication that contributes to students' bullying tendencies. According to Loughlin-Presnal and Bierman (2018), positive parental expectation increases their children's behavioral engagement. Ma, Siu, and Tse (2018) also stipulated that parental expectations encourage parental support. Further, parental expectation also contributes to students' behavioral problems and depression. Ohene, Ireland, McNeely, and Borowsky (2006) also mentioned that parental expectation might lead the adolescents' attitudes toward interpersonal peer violence, intentions to fight, physical fighting, bullying, or violence victimization.

However, parental discipline and parental communication show no significant association with all domains of bullying tendencies. This coincides with the study of Broll and Reynolds (2021), which stipulated that parental influence does not necessarily associate with bullying tendencies. Thus, parental style is not the only factor affecting individuals' engagement in bullying. There are several existing factors other than the parental influence that triggered to commit bullying. Personality traits, peers, and outside home environment also contribute risk of committing bullying behavior.

5.4 Significant Impact of Parental Influence on Bullying Tendencies

Another important objective of the study is to ascertain which domain of parental influence significantly predicts the bullying tendency among high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT). The impact of

parental influence on bullying tendencies was analyzed using multi-regression analysis. Overall, the result revealed that in both comprehensive and individual measurements, parental influence significantly predicts bullying tendencies inversely. This suggests that increased parental influence leads to lower bullying tendencies. Moreover, this implies that when a parent shows good communication, positive discipline, and especially positive expectations towards their children, it reduces bullying behaviors. Undeniably, several authors (Ajani & Dosunmu, 2018; Chiarlitti & Kolen, 2017; Yuksel-Sahin, 2015) have stipulated that when a parent treats their children in a forceful or dictatorial manner, using extreme or unjust punishments, commanding many restrictions, and enforcing punitive rules, their children are more likely to display aloof, unfriendly, aggressive, violent, and a tendency to commit bullying behaviors. They become rebellious and non-compliant kind of personalities and engage in bullying acts.

The current findings likewise concur with the propositions of well-known researchers (Tajuddin, Utami, & Arafat, 2017; Efobi & Nwokolo, 2014; Shetgiri, Lin, Avila, & Flores, 2012; Knous-Westfall, Ehrensaft, MacDonell, & Cohen, 2012; Baldry, Farrington, & Sorrentino, 2017) that established the significant impact of parental influence on tendency to bullying behavior. They have claimed that the lack of good parenting practices, lack of parental communication, support, pressure, and discipline significantly lead to children's risk of committing bullying behavior or doing bullying deeds. Likewise, this confirms Swearer and Hymel's (2015) findings that when a child is abused, exposed to intimate partner violence, poor parental supervision, lack of parental communication, lack of parental emotional support, negative family environment, parental conflict, and domestic violence, parental abuse, authoritarian parenting, and inappropriate discipline contribute to or are associated with bullying perpetration.

Baldry, Farrington, and Sorrentino (2017) and Tajuddin, Utami, and Arafat (2017) expressed that bullying offender usually comes from families with low relationships, little warmth, presence of an absent father, need for high power, family dysfunction, aggressive behavior, and poor of parental support, communication, and discipline. They also stipulate that those who became bullied individuals were usually raised with authoritarian parenting. In most cases, their parents often use violence as a form of discipline against child behavior, such as punitive verbal and physical punishment and being neglected.

Moreover, the present results of the study were likewise parallel with the works of Papanikolaou, Chatzikosma, and Kleio (2011), which demonstrated that students' involvement in bullying incidents increases when there is no punishment despite the child's misbehavior or when parents enforce the discipline methods without justification. Moreover, bullying occurs due to parents' reluctance to provide assistance on issues, problems, and stress that child they have experienced in both school and home.

When examined independently, only *parental expectations* significantly influenced bullying tendencies. This further suggests that in the context of this study, *the parental expectation* is the critical factor that affects the bullying tendencies of the students. As mentioned earlier, parental expectation can play an important role in children/adolescents' aggressive behavior (Ohene, Ireland, McNeely, & Borowsky, 2006; Loughlin-Presnal & Bierman, 2018; Ma, Siu, & Tse, 2018).

However, *parental discipline* and *parental communication* do not affect the bullying tendencies of the students. As mentioned a while ago, several factors can affect bullying tendencies, not solely parental influence (Broll & Reynolds, 2021). Thus, according to Papanikolaou, Chatzikosma, and Kleio (2011), peer, family, school, community, and cultural environments influence children's behavior.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Conclusion

The following conclusion is drawn based on the results of the present study. The study ascertained that the level of parental influence is high. This means that the high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology perceived their parents as having positive parental expectations, good disciplining methods, and communicating with them regularly about issues and problems, especially school matters. On the other hand, bullying tendency was observed to be very low. This means that majority of the high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology never committed any bullying acts.

When correlated, the test of relationship revealed that parental influence is associated with bullying tendency; thus, the first null hypothesis is rejected. This means that parents' expectations, discipline, and communication contribute to students' bullying tendencies. On the other hand, the findings revealed that parental influence significantly predicts bullying tendencies; thus, the second null hypothesis was also rejected. This further explained that parental influence could cause the risk of committing bullying behavioral acts.

As a result, the findings validate the social learning theory of Bandura (1977) as cited by Chen, Wang, & Hung (2015). Social learning theory suggests that people can learn new behaviors by observing others. This theory is based on

the idea that we learn from our interactions with others in a social context. Using this theory, the learning from the interaction in a social context (observational learning) can be related to parental influence, where students affect their behaviors through observing and experiencing their parent's behaviors. Thus, the outcomes such as students' belief that exhibiting this behavior similar to their parents relate to bullying tendencies.

Moreover, the findings also validated the attachment theory of Bowlby (1907-1990) as cited by Bretherton (1985). Attachment theory addresses the establishment, maintenance, and consequences of the affectionate relationship of a child towards their parents. It must be proven that this affectionate relationship of the parents towards their children relates to parental influence, specifically in the way how parents discipline, communicate, support, and care for their children in addressing behavioral, psychological, and emotional development. Thus, this established attachment, either positive or negative consequences, relates to bullying tendencies where the possible outcome of parent-child relationships.

Finally, the present findings also validated the social control theory of Hirschi (1969), as cited by Houser (2021). The theory suggests that when individuals are less likely to manifest bullying behaviors if they have strong social bonds to the conventional society. Thus, these elements which constitute the societal bond can be related to parental influence in a way that parental bonds towards their children include their level of attachment, commitment, involvement, and parent's belief in discipline, how to care, how to support and encourage their children to diminish their children's propensity for deviant behavior which relates to the risk of committing aggressive behavior or bullying tendency.

6.2 Recommendation

The present researchers would recommend regarding the students' perceptions of parental influence and bullying tendencies as provided by the survey data.

To the parents, they should continually communicate, support, and discipline their children at all times and lower their expectations so that their sons and daughters will not feel so much pressure since, in this present study, the parental expectation is significantly associated with and predictor of bullying tendencies.

To the teachers, though the result shows that the high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology are low in bullying tendencies, it is also recommended that they monitor the behaviors of the students towards their classmates to prevent bullying.

To the school and guidance counselor, the researchers recommend continuing the bullying campaign and awareness such as anti-bullying seminars for the students and religious activities to maintain the low risk of the bullying tendencies among the high school students of San Agustin Institute of Technology.

Lastly, the researchers would recommend to future researchers to expand the scope of this investigation by including other variables that could potentially influence a different result. Future researchers may conduct studies among public and academic institutions using different methodological approaches, contexts, and participants. In this way, a comparison can be made for confirmation or otherwise.

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